

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF FURANO COMPOUNDS. PART XI.
CYCLODEHYDRATION OF 2-ACYL-3-BENZYLCOUMARONES

By J. N. CHATTERJEA AND S. K. ROY *

2-Acyl-3-benzylcoumarones have been prepared and their cyclodehydration² to β -brazans studied.

In this communication, the synthesis of β -brazans by aromatic cyclodehydration of 2-acyl-3-benzylcoumarones, as described in an earlier paper (*this Journal*, 1953, 30, 1), has been re-examined and extended to a few more cases with a view to studying the scope and limitations of the method. The method appears to be of general application provided that the 2-acylcoumarones are readily synthetically available, and in difficult cases, the Kipping cyclisation of the related 3-benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid affords the alternative solution.

3-Benzylcoumarones, which afford the 2-acylcoumarones by the Hoesch or the Gattermann synthesis, are best prepared by the decarboxylation of the corresponding 2-carboxylic acids. For instance, 6-methoxy-3-benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid (I: R = COOH; R' = OMe; R'' = H), prepared by Bentley and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1355), gave on decarboxylation with the aid of copper-bronze, 6-methoxy-3-benzylcoumarone which furnished 2-formyl derivative on the Gattermann reaction. The

orientation of this aldehyde was established by its preparation from the corresponding acid, mentioned above, by the Stevens-McFadeyn method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 584)

* In part.

involving the decomposition of the sulphonhydrazide (I: R = CONHNHSO₂Ph; R' = OMe; R'' = H) prepared *via* the ester and the hydrazide in the usual manner. On cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid, the aldehyde afforded 3-methoxy- β -brazan in rather a poor yield. It may be noted, however, that the isolation of 3-methoxy-6-hydroxy- β -brazan in substance from the coumarilic acid also proved very difficult (cf. Bentley and Robinson, *loc. cit.*). This has been achieved albeit in unsatisfactory yield, by the cyclisation of the related acid chloride in cold benzene and identified by oxidation to 3-methoxy- β -brazan-quinone, synthesised earlier (*this Journal*, 1954, 31, 101).

3-(3':4'-Dimethoxybenzyl)-6 : 7-dimethoxycoumarone has been prepared from 2-hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethoxyphenyl-(3':4'-dimethoxybenzyl)-ketone in the usual manner. The latter was prepared by the interaction of homoveratroyl chloride with pyrogallol trimethyl ether in dry ether with the aid of aluminium chloride. This coumarone was successfully converted into the 2-formyl derivative which gave 3 : 4 : 8 : 9-tetramethoxy- β -brazan (II, a possible derivative of haematoxylin) in quantitative yield on cyclodehydration with phosphoric acid.

Our experience with the simplest case, however, has been very unusual. 3-Benzylcoumarone (Chatterjea, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 265) has now been prepared from the keto-nitrile (III), obtained by the condensation of *o*-methoxybenzoic ester and phenylacetonitrile. On treatment with boiling hydrobromic acid in acetic acid, this nitrile furnished a mixture of *o*-hydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone (IV) and 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (V), separable by steam-distillation or by taking advantage of the latter's solubility in alkali carbonate. The former was converted into 3-benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid and thence by decarboxylation (copper-quinoline) to 3-benzylcoumarone. As reported earlier (Chatterjea, *loc. cit.*), the Gattermann reaction failed entirely with this coumarone*; a trace of the aldehyde was obtained on employing the modified reaction (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1830; 1939, 132). Alternatively, attempts were made to prepare this aldehyde from the corresponding 2-carboxylic acid. The Rosenmund reaction having yielded a very impure product, recourse was taken to apply the Stevens-McFadyen procedure as before. Accordingly, the acid was esterified with diazomethane or methanolic sulphuric acid, but the corresponding hydrazide could never be obtained on treating the ester with hydrazine hydrate. The sole product (m. p. 196°), obtained in excellent yield, contained a high percentage of nitrogen, analysing for C₁₁H₁₀O₂N₂. This compound behaved as a hydrazide in as much as it reduced Fehling's solution and afforded the original acid on alkaline hydrolysis. It is difficult at this stage to suggest the correct constitution of this extraordinary compound; a sulphonhydrazide, derived from it, also did not analyse correctly, and failed to provide any aldehyde by decomposition in ethyleneglycol under various conditions. Further work is necessary to elucidate the nature of this abnormal compound. A more encouraging result was obtained by reducing the *N*-methylanilide of the acid with lithium aluminium hydride and hydrolysing the product with acid (cf. Friedman, Abstracts, 116th National Meeting, 5M, 1949; Weygand *et al.*, *Angew Chem.*, 1953, 65, 525). The aldehyde was obtained in rather

** Formylations of this coumarone and allied compounds with dimethylformamide have been more fruitful. The results will be communicated shortly.

an impure condition which gave a small quantity of β -brazan on cyclodehydration with hydrobromic acid in acetic acid.

2-Acetyl-3-benzylcoumarone was prepared in impure condition from the acid chloride (I: R=COCl; R'=R''=H) and magnesium malonic ester (cf. Walker and Hauser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1386). Attempts to cyclise this ketone so as to obtain 6-methyl- β -brazan have been so far abortive.

Cyclisation of 3-benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid by way of the acid chloride was extremely facile and the product 6-hydroxy- β -brazan was obtained in excellent yield. This compound was converted into β -brazan or the related quinone by reduction or oxidation.

EXPERIMENTAL *

6-Methoxy-3-benzylcoumarone.—6-Methoxy-3-benzylcoumarilic acid (Bentley and Robinson, *loc. cit.*) was heated with a trace of copper-bronze in a metal bath at 220° till the evolution of carbon dioxide was substantially complete, and then distilled in vacuum. The colorless product (yield 50%) solidified immediately and obtained in prisms, m. p. 54° from methanol. The compound gave yellow coloration with sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 81.1; H, 5.6. C₁₈H₁₄O₂ requires C, 80.7; H, 5.9%).

6-Methoxy-2-formyl-3-benzylcoumarone: *Method (a).*—The foregoing coumarone (1.5 g.) in dry ether (40 c.c.) containing ZnCl₂ (1 g.) and HCN (4 c.c.) was saturated with anhydrous HCl gas at 0°. The colour of the mixture turned from brown to reddish brown and finally again brown. The crystalline aldimine hydrochloride was collected next day, washed with dry ether, decomposed with water (50 c.c.) and warmed on the water-bath. The crystalline product was filtered, crystallised from alcohol and the aldehyde was obtained in colorless needles, m. p. 107°, developing a green colour with H₂SO₄. (Found: C, 77.0; H, 5.6. C₁₇H₁₄O₃ requires C, 76.7; H, 5.3%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in maroon plates, m. p. 213°. (Found: N, 13.0. C₂₃H₁₆O₆N₄ requires N, 12.6%).

Method (b).—6-Methoxy-3-benzylcoumarilic acid (3.0 g.) was esterified by boiling with methanolic H₂SO₄ (30 c.c., 8%) for 6 hours. Isolated as usual, the ester (3.0 g.) had no tendency to crystallise. This was then boiled with a mixture of alcohol (15 c.c.) and hydrazine hydrate (10 c.c., 60%, commercial) for 6 hours on the water-bath and then poured into water. The hydrazide (I: R=CONHNH₂; R'=OMe; R''=H) which solidified gradually was collected after 48 hours and obtained in colorless needles (2.2 g.), m. p. 144-48° from alcohol. (Found: N, 9.9. C₁₇H₁₆O₃N₂ requires N, 9.5%). A solution of the hydrazide (2.0 g.) in dry pyridine (12 c.c.) was treated at 0° with benzylsulphonyl chloride (1.2 g.), left in the refrigerator for 4 hours and then poured into iced HCl, affording the sulphonhydrazide (I: R=CONHNHSO₂Ph; R'=OMe; R''=H) (2.5 g.) which was collected after washing with cold alcohol. The compound was obtained in colorless prisms, m. p. 254-55° (decomp.) from a large volume of alcohol. (Found: N, 6.9. C₂₃H₂₀O₆N₂S requires N, 6.4%). A suspension of the sulphonhydrazide (0.6 g.) in ethyleneglycol (15 c.c.) at 160° was treated with anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.5 g.). The vigorous reaction that ensued was quenched after 80 seconds.

* All m. p.'s are uncorrected.

by pouring into water. The aldehyde was isolated with ether and obtained in colorless needles (0.15 g.), m.p. and mixed m. p. 107°.

3-Methoxy- β -brazan.—The above aldehyde (1.0 g.) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (10 c.c.) at 100° for 2 hours. The colour of the mixture turned blue from green. After pouring into water, the precipitated compound was collected and purified by several crystallisations from alcohol. The pure product (m.p. 205°) was obtained in a poor yield (Kostanecki and Lampe *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 2373, record m.p. 205°).

Cyclisation of 6-Methoxy-3-benzylcoumarilic Acid.—If the acid is cyclised through the acid chloride in cold CS₂ with AlCl₃, 3-methoxy-6-hydroxy- β -brazan is formed, as detected by typical colour reaction with chloroform and alkali. But the isolation of the pure material was not possible in any of the experiments. The crude sulphur-containing mass on oxidation with chromic acid in acetic acid gave 3-methoxy- β -brazanquinone which readily crystallised from pyridine in golden yellow plates, m. p. and mixed m.p. 292°. (Found: C, 73.2, 73.2; H, 3.8, 3.7. Calc. for C₁₇H₁₆O₄: C, 73.3; H, 3.6%). A better result was obtained when the cyclisation was done in benzene. The acid chloride (from acid, 2.0 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.) was cooled to 0° and treated with AlCl₃ (3 g.) and left overnight. On working up, a dirty solid product was obtained giving a positive colour reaction. This, on crystallisation from acetic acid, gave a product as colorless needles (0.15 g.), m. p. 225-26°, showing a negative colour reaction. (Found: C, 78.4, 78.4; H, 4.7, 4.9%). This compound is soluble in alkali, insoluble in sodium bicarbonate and gave a positive test for the methoxyl group and developed a yellow colour with H₂SO₄, turning to darkish pink. The mother-liquor was evaporated, the mass extracted with alkali and acidified. The amorphous mass was treated with warm alcohol, cooled and separated from a small quantity of crystals (the foregoing byproduct, m. p. 225°) and the filtrate allowed to evaporate slowly in a refrigerator. The crystals separating were collected (positive colour reaction with chloroform and alkali), pressed on the porous plate and crystallised from a small quantity of dilute alcohol, when 3-methoxy-6-hydroxy- β -brazan was obtained in cream-coloured leaflets, m. p. 183-84°. This could not be analysed due to shortage of material.

2-Hydroxy-3:4-dimethoxyphenyl-(3':4'-dimethoxybenzyl) Ketone.—AlCl₃ (anhyd., 4 g.) was dissolved carefully in ice-cold dry ether (30 c.c.) and then 1:2:3-trimethoxybenzene (4.6 g.) was added to it in the cold. Homoveratroyl chloride (5.1 g.) in ether (15 c.c.) was added to the cooled stirred mixture. The violet colour which appeared at first changed to brown. After stirring for 4 hours in the cold, the mixture was left overnight and then decomposed after 30 hours. The ketone, isolated as usual, showed a violet ferric reaction. Crystallised from alcohol this was obtained in colorless needles (2.6 g.), m. p. 135-34°. (Found: C, 64.6; H, 6.2; C₁₈H₂₀O₆ requires C, 65.1; H, 6.0%),

6:7-Dimethoxy-3(3':4'-dimethoxybenzyl)coumarone-2-carboxylic Acid.—A mixture of the above ketone (3.1 g.), anhydrous acetone (40 c.c.), dry potassium carbonate (10 g.) and ethyl bromoacetate (4 c.c.) was refluxed for 6 hours. The oily product was taken up in ether, washed with sodium carbonate, dried and the solvent removed. After

removing the excess of ethyl bromoacetate in vacuum at 160° , the residue was dissolved in dry alcohol (20 c.c.) and added to alcoholic sodium ethoxide (sodium 0.4 g. and alcohol 10 c.c.) and refluxed for 1 hour. After removing most of the alcohol, the mixture was boiled with aqueous alcoholic sodium hydroxide (10 c.c., 10%) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. On acidification a gum was obtained which solidified in contact with acetic acid. The acid was obtained as a chalky mass (1.8 g.) which, when crystallised from acetic acid, was obtained in wooly needles, m. p. $195-95^{\circ}$. With H_2SO_4 the compound gave a pink coloration. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 5.5. $C_{20}H_{20}O_7$ requires C, 64.5; H, 5.4%).

6: 7-Dimethoxy-3-(3': 4'-dimethoxybenzyl)-2-formylcoumarone.—6:7-Dimethoxy-3-(3': 4'-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumarone was obtained as a glass (yield ca. 40%) by decarboxylating the above coumarilic acid by heating above its melting point with a trace of copper-bronze and distilling the product in vacuum. The crude product (0.4 g.) was dissolved in ether (10 c.c.) containing $ZnCl_2$ (0.3 g.), treated with anhydrous HCN (1 c.c.) and then saturated at 0° with HCl gas. The green sticky product was washed with dry ether, decomposed with hot water and the crude aldehyde obtained as a gum (0.25 g.), showing a red coloration with sulphuric acid and turning green immediately. The dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in red plates, m. p. 214° . (Found: N, 9.9. $C_{26}H_{24}O_6N_4$ requires N, 10.5%).

3: 4: 8: 9-Tetramethoxy- β -brazan (II).—The crude aldehyde (0.2 g.), obtained above, was heated with syrupy phosphoric acid (5 c.c.) for 20 minutes at 100° . The mass became greenish and a crystalline product separated quickly. Water (20 c.c.) was added and the product collected and purified by chromatography on alumina in benzene solution. The violet fluorescent band (in U. V. light) was eluted with benzene (ca. 100 c.c.) and the crystalline product was obtained from acetic acid in colorless plates (0.17 g.), m. p. 244° . (Found: C, 71.6; H, 5.6. $C_{26}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 71.0; H, 5.3%). With sulphuric acid the compound developed a green coloration.

o-Hydroxyphenylbenzyl Ketone.—A mixture of phenylacetonitrile (3.0 g.) and ethyl *o*-methoxybenzoate (3.8 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.) was added to alcohol-free sodium ethoxide (sodium, 0.5 g.) and refluxed for 4 hours. On cooling, the sodium salt of the keto-nitrile (III) separated. The mixture was treated with iced water, the aqueous layer separated and acidified to furnish the keto-nitrile in nearly quantitative yield, crystallising from alcohol in colorless prisms, m. p. 115° . (Found: N, 5.5. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 5.6%). The nitrile (2.0 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of HBr (10 c.c., 48%) and acetic acid (10 c.c.) and refluxed for 3 hours. The mixture was poured into water and cooled. The solid was collected and distilled in a current of steam. *o*-Hydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone was obtained from the distillate in a pure condition (1.0 g.), m. p. 59° , exhibiting a violet ferric reaction (Skraup and Binder, *Ber.*, 1929, 62, 1127, record m. p. 57°). The residual solid in the flask was identified as 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (V), which was crystallised from alcohol in colorless prisms or plates, m. p. 234° (Pauly and Lockemann, *Ber.*, 1915, 48, 28, record m. p. 236° ; Stahmann *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2286, record m. p. $234-35^{\circ}$). (Found: C, 75.7; H, 4.4. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{10}O_3$: C, 75.6; H, 4.2%). The coumarin can also be extracted from an ethereal solution of the mixture with aqueous sodium carbonate. The acetyl derivative was

obtained in colorless needles, m. p. 182° from ethanol. (Found: C, 72.4; H, 4.7. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.3%). The *benzoyl* derivative (prepared in pyridine) was obtained in colorless plates, m. p. 205° from alcohol. (Found: C, 77.6; H, 4.1. $C_{22}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 77.2; H, 4.1%).

3-Benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylic Acid.—The phenol (IV: 20 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (150 c.c.) with potassium carbonate (55 g.) and ethyl bromoacetate (20 c.c.) for 7 hours. The phenoxyacetic ester, isolated with ether, was obtained as a colorless viscous oil which was next treated with alcoholic sodium ethoxide (sodium 3.0 g. and alcohol 260 c.c.) and refluxed for 1 hour. To this mixture was then added 5% NaOH (50 c.c.) and refluxed for another hour. Alcohol was removed by distillation and the residue acidified after dilution; the resulting gum was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, furnishing the *acid* (13.5-16.6 g.) as thick plates, m. p. 206° . (Found: C, 75.7; H, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.8%). The compound developed gradually a reddish yellow colour with sulphuric acid. The *methyl ester*, prepared with methanolic H_2SO_4 , crystallised from methanol in colorless prisms, m. p. $81-82^{\circ}$ (labile, not obtained in subsequent experiments) and m. p. 123° (stable). (Found: C, 76.5; H, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.6; H, 5.2%). With diazomethane, the stable variety of the ester was isolated. The ester did not give any coloration with H_2SO_4 . The *p-toluidide*, prepared by way of the acid chloride in benzene solution, was obtained in clusters of colorless needles, m. p. 253° from acetic acid and analysed for high nitrogen content. (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{23}H_{18}O_2N$ requires N, 4.1%).

3-Benzylcoumarone.—The above coumarilic acid could not be decarboxylated by heating above the melting point with copper-bronze; the original material was recovered. The acid (7 g.) was boiled with quinoline (35 c.c.) in presence of copper-bronze (0.5 g.) for $3\frac{1}{2}$ hours, cooled, filtered, acidified and extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed successively with dilute acid and alkali, dried and distilled in vacuum. The product (1.1 g., recovered acid, ca. 4 g.) was obtained as a colorless liquid, b. p. $172-74^{\circ}/4.2$ mm, which solidified and obtained in prisms from methanol, m. p. 52° . (Chatterjea, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 265, records b. p. $170-75^{\circ}/12$ mm, which appears to be in error). The compound gave a yellow coloration with H_2SO_4 . (Found: C, 86.0; H, 5.7. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{12}O$: C, 86.5; H, 5.8%).

Gattermann Reaction with 3-Benzylcoumarone.—The coumarone (1.0 g.) in pure dry ether (15 c.c.) was treated successively with $ZnCl_2$ (0.2 g.), $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 0.5 g.), powdered KCl (0.1 g.) and HCN (1.5 c.c.) and saturated at 0° with dry HCl and left in the refrigerator for 2 days. There was no characteristic change in colour. A trace of a sticky material separating was washed with ether and then decomposed with water (4 c.c.) on the water-bath. A trace of *2-formyl-3-benzylcoumarone* was obtained which was isolated with ether and converted into *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone*, m. p. $244-45^{\circ}$ from acetic acid. The sample was not analysed due to shortage of material.

Action of Hydrazine on Ethyl 3-Benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylate.—A mixture of the ester (5 g.), alcohol (25 c.c.) and hydrazine hydrate (12 c.c., 60%) was refluxed for 6 hours on the water-bath and then poured into water. The crystalline product (5 g.) was collected, crystallised twice from alcohol and obtained in colorless needles, m. p.

196°. (Found: C, 65.6, 65.7; H, 5.6, 5.6; N, 18.7. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2N_2$ (hydrazide) requires C, 72.2; H, 5.3; N, 10.5%; $C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_4$ requires C, 64.9; H, 5.4; N, 18.8%). The compound reduced Fehling's solution and gave on alkaline hydrolysis (2 hours), 3-benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid, m. p. and mixed m.p. 206°. On interaction with benzene-sulphonyl chloride in pyridine (using molecular proportions) a *sulphonhydrazide* was obtained, crystallising from methanol in transparent prisms (turning opaque on drying), m. p. 235°. (Found: N, 9.1%). Several experiments were carried out to decompose this sulphonhydrazide in ethyleneglycol with sodium carbonate, potassium carbonate and borax but no aldehyde could be detected in any of the experiments.

2-Formyl-3-benzylcoumarone.—3-Benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid was converted into the *N-methylanilide* by the interaction of the acid chloride with methylaniline in boiling benzene for 8 hours. Crystallised from alcohol, the compound was obtained in colorless prisms, m. p. 148-49°, but the analysis was not satisfactory. (Found: N, 5.1. $C_{22}H_{19}O_2N$ requires N, 4.1%). A solution of the compound in tetrahydrofuran was carefully stirred and treated at the ordinary temperature with a solution of lithium aluminium hydride (*M/4*) in the same solvent. After stirring for 15 minutes, the mixture was carefully decomposed with HCl. The product obtained on working up contained a small quantity of the aldehyde which afforded the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 244-45° (from acetic acid). (Found: C, 64.2; H, 4.2. $C_{22}H_{16}O_5N_4$ requires C, 63.5; H, 3.9%).

β-Brazan.—The crude aldehyde (0.08 g.) was boiled under reflux with a mixture of acetic acid (2 c.c.) and hydrobromic acid (1.5 c.c., 48%) for 3 hours. The product obtained on dilution was collected, dried and chromatographed on an alumina column. *β-Brazan* was obtained in a pure condition (*ca.* 4 mg.), m.p. 207-208° after crystallisation from benzene-alcohol. (Found: C, 87.9; H, 4.5. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{16}O$: C, 88.1; H, 4.5%).

2-Acetyl-3-benzylcoumarone.—3-Benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid was converted into the *ketone*, following closely the method of Walker and Hauser (*loc. cit.*). The crude ketone was obtained as a gum which did not crystallise. The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in orange-red needles, m.p. 240-41°. (Found: N, 12.6. $C_{23}H_{20}O_5N_4$ requires N, 12.9%). The cyclodehydration of this compound with hydrobromic acid was not possible.

6-Hydroxy-β-brazan.—3-Benzylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid (0.6 g.) was converted into the acid chloride in CS_2 solution (5 c.c.) with thionyl chloride (3 c.c.) and then the volatile materials were removed in vacuum. The oily residue was dissolved in CS_2 (25 c.c.), cooled in ice and gradually treated with excess of $AlCl_3$ (2 g.) and left overnight. After removing the solvent by decantation, the residue was decomposed with iced HCl and the crystalline product collected and washed with sodium carbonate solution. *6-Hydroxy-β-brazan* (0.5 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in cream-coloured needles, m.p. 195°. (Found: C, 82.6; H, 4.6. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 82.0; H 4.3%). The compound developed a green coloration with chloroform and alkali.

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish needles, m. p. 147°. (Found: C, 78.8; H, 4.3. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 78.3; H, 4.3%).

On boiling this hydroxy compound (0.2 g.) with hydriodic acid (5 c.c., *d* 1.7) for 2 hours, β -brazan was obtained in excellent yield (0.15 g.), crystallising from benzene-alcohol in colorless plates, m. p. 207°.

β -Brazanquinone.—The foregoing hydroxy compound (0.2 g.) in boiling acetic acid (5 c.c.) was treated with a solution of chromic acid (0.25 g.) in water (1.2 c.c.), refluxed for 2 minutes and then the solution was cooled. The quinone was obtained in yellow needles, m. p. and mixed m.p. 242°. (Found: C, 77.3; H, 3.3. Calc. for $C_{18}H_8O_3$: C, 77.4; H, 3.2 per cent).

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SCIENCE COLLEGE, PATNA-5.

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